

Review of Sarcophagidae (Diptera) of North African countries with new faunistic data from Algeria

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Abstract

A total of 199 sarcophagid species are listed from North African region, including Algeria (84 species), Azores (17), Canary Is. (33), Ceuta & Melilla (2), Egypt (116), Libya (24), Madeira Is. (7), Malta (43), Morocco (49), and Tunisia (45). 20 species have been collected in Oum El Bouaghi forest, including one species new for science (*Sarcophila khrokalo* sp. n.) and 10 species first recorded from Algeria (*Metopia argyrocephala*, *Paragusia multipunctata*, *Phrosinella fedtshenkoi*, *Helicophagella novercoides*, *Artamonoviella monspellensia*, *Heteronychia uncicurva*, *Thyrocneema belgiana*, *Liosarcophaga catalunya*, *L. portschinskyi*, *L. teretirostris*).

Keywords: *Sarcophagidae*, North Africa, Algeria, fauna, new species.

Received: 5 July 2019; Revised: 19 November 2019; Online: 31 December 2019

Introduction

Altogether (including present data) 199 sarcophagid species (Enderlein (1928), Lehrer (1995, 2003a), Pape (1996); Povolný, 1992; Rohdendorf (1930, 1935, 1937, 1971, 1975), Salem (1938a, b), Séguy (1941a, b), Sotiraki *et al.* (2010), Verves (1982, 1985, 1986, 1993a, b), Verves & Khrokalo (2006, 2015, 2017), Verves *et al.* (2015), Villeneuve (1910, 1912a, b), Whitmore (2011) have been recorded from the North African territory. Country faunas from within this region have been explored by many authors, the most significant ones being: Egypt (Abd El-Halim *et al.*, 2005, 2009; Becker, 1902, 1903; El-Ahmady *et al.*, 2015; El-Hawagry & El-Azab, 2019; Helal *et al.*, 1981; Lehrer 2003a; Mohamed & Abdel-Rahman, 1985; Rohdendorf, 1934; Salem, 1935, 1936, 1940; Salwa & Abdel-Rahman, 1983; Shaumar & Kamal, 1984; Steyskal & El-Bialy, 1967; Tantawi *et al.*, 1996, 2018); Libya (Séguy, 1935; Venturi, 1960); Malta (Gatt & Ebejer, 2014; Schembri *et al.*, 1991; Venturi, 1960; Villeneuve, 1910; Wyatt, 1991), Tunisia (Bezzi, 1922; Gatt & Ebejer, 2014; Mathis, 1957; Séguy, 1934), Spanish North Africa (Peris *et al.*, 1996), Morocco (Becker & Stein, 1914; Delanoë, 1922; El-Abrak *et al.*, 2002; El-Mezouari *et al.*, 2014; Farkas *et al.*, 2003; Lmimouni *et al.*, 2004; Romli *et al.*, 2010;

Séguy, 1930, 1939, 1940a, b, 1941c, d, 1949, 1953; Tliqui *et al.*, 2007; Verves, 1993b), Canary Is. (Báez, 1980; Báez & García, 2004; Becker, 1908a; Carles-Tolrá, 2002, Lehrer & Báez, 1986; Peris *et al.*, 1996, 2001; Verves & Barták, 2017; Villeneuve, 1908), Madeira Is. (Becker, 1908b; Pape, 1986, 1990), Azores (Séguy, 1936; Kehlmaier, 1998). A brief review of studies of Algerian sarcophagids with a checklist of 74 species was published in my previous article (Verves, 2017). To compile the existing data here I present a checklist of 84 species.

Materials and Methods

The commune of Oum El Bouaghi is located in the north-east of Algeria in the Constantine Highlands on area of 7638.13 km². This commune is located in the high Constantine plains, between the mountain regions. It bends from the north to the south where it passes from an altitude of 1635 m (Jebel sidiR'ghiss) in the North, to 808m (Garaa of Tarf) to the South. 57 specimens of sarcophagids have been collected in Oum El Bouaghi forest, 1210 m, 35.899, 7.129, pt., iv.2016, by Mr. N. Baba Aissa and were sent to me by Prof. Miroslav Barták (Czech University of Life Sciences, Praha) for study. Author follows classification of Verves (1986)

and Verves & Khrokalo (2006) in order of species in check list. The material was examined under Nikon SMZ 1500 stereozoom microscope.

Abbreviations of morphological features: *acr* - acrostichal seta; *ad* - anterodorsal seta; *ap* - apical seta; *bas* - basal seta; *d* - discal seta; *dc* - dorsocentral seta; *dm-cu* - discal medial cubital crossvein; *f₂* - mid femur; *fr* - frontal seta; *h* - humeral seta; *ia* - intraalar seta; *ivt* - inner vertical seta; *kepst* - katepisternal seta; *M* - medial vein; *npl* - notopleural seta; *oc* - ocellar seta; *orb* - orbital seta; *ovt* - outer vertical seta; *ph* - posthumeral seta; *poc* - postocellar seta; *pocl* - postorbital seta; *R₁* - first longitudinal vein; *R₂₊₃* - second longitudinal vein; *R₄₊₅* - third longitudinal vein; *r₅* - first posterior cell; *subap* - subapical seta; *t₁* - fore tibia.

I provide here a checklist of Sarcophagidae for all the North African countries (Table 1).

Results

Description of a new species

Sarcophila khrokaloae Verves, sp. n.

Figures: 1-2

[urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:40F60453-31A3-488C-A4AE-22258D720D30](https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-22258720/v1)

Male. Head: Black, thickly silver grey pollinated; antennae and palpi black. Eyes bare, dichoptic, separated at vertex 0.40×, at level of antennal base 0.36× of head width. Frontal vitta 1.67× widened backward, matt grey, with distinct grey-silver dusting around matt black ocellar triangle, about 2× as wide as one of parafrontalia just in front of anterior ocellus. Parafrontalia silver grey dusted, in addition to strong *orb* and *fr*, and with a longitudinal row of 4-6 small setae along the edge of the eye between the fore *orb* and fore *fr*. Two regular rows of *pocl* present; *fr* 6; *orb* 2+1; *oc* strong and long, directed laterodorsally; *poc* weak and elongate; *ovt* and *ivt* well developed. Parafacialia at level of antennal base 0.26× of head length, silver grey dusted, with a single irregular row of the mid-long fine black setae. Face distinctly widened forwardly to vibrissal angles, silver grey dusted, with broad facial carina. Facial ridge bare, vibrissae well developed. Genae 0.22× of head-height, thickly silver-grey dusted, clothed with numerous black setae. Genal groove

blackish grey, bare. Postgenae black, largely clothed with mid-long black hairs. Occiput black, covered with black hairs. Pedicel matt black, its surface across pedicelar bristle orange yellow. First flagellomere matt black, about 1.8-2.0× as long as pedicel. Arista widened in basal 1/3, black, long plumose. Palpi entirely black, distinctly widened apically.

Thorax: Black, light grey-dusted, covered with black hairs. Dorsum marked with broad median, a pair of approximated narrow submedian and two lateral broad longitudinal black stripes on prescutum and scutum, each more distinctly visible when viewed from behind; only the median one reaches the end of scutellum. Humeri, notopleura, sternopleura and scutellum distinctly yellowish grey-dusted; thoracic spiracles yellowish white. Prosternum and propleuron bare, the other pleura with setae. *acr* 1+1; *dc* 2+3; *ia* 0+3; *h* 3; *ph* 1, *npl* 2, *kepst* 2+1. Scutellum with long strong pair of *ap* and more short fine *subap*, *bas* and *d*.

Wings: Membrane hyaline; veins yellowish brown; epaulet and basicosta yellowish white; subcostal sclerite yellowish brown. Costal spine small, unclear; *R₁* and *R₂₊₃* bare; *R₄₊₅* with a row of black setae from basal node to the intersection with *r-m* above; node of *R₂₊₃* and *R₄₊₅* with a few black setae below. The ratio of 3rd and 5th costal sections is 1:1.4. Cell *r₅* open; the last section of *M* curved at a blunt almost right angle; *dm-cu* sigmoid. Both calypteres white, slightly grayish, halteres yellow.

Legs: Black. Claws curved, distinctly shortened than 5th tarsomere; pulvilli ovale equal to claws in length; *t₁* with 3 *ad*; *f₂* without ctenidium.

Abdomen: Grey dusted, with shining black dorsal drawing. 1+2nd tergite with 3 (medial and two lateral) longitudinal bands; each of 3rd-5th tergites with 3 triangled hind spots. Middle longitudinal spots reach to the fore margins of 3rd and 4th tergites, and lateral spots oval, located in hind 0.5-0.6; 5th tergite with 3 rounded unclear spots in hind part.

Terminalia: Black, grey dusted. Narrowed apical part of cercus subulate, not serrated, shorter than widened basal one. Surstylus is separated by a deep oval cut on the upper and lower parts; the latter carries a vertical row of setae from the cut to the lower corner and numerous apical hairs (Fig. 1). Pregonites s-

like curved, pointed on apex; postgonites leaf-shaped in the apical part, with numerous hairs bearing particular dorsolateral site. Aedeagus with short apical hook and special membrane lobe located below. Hypophallus consists of a thickened hairy basal part and a narrow and long rod-shaped apical one located at an obtuse angle (Fig. 2).

Female: unknown.

Measurement: Holotype (male): Body length: 5.5 mm.

Etymology: The specific name is given in honour of my wife, well known Ukrainian entomologist Dr. Liudmyla A. Khrokalo (National Technical University of Ukraine "Igor Sikorsky Kyiv Polytechnic Institute", Kyiv, Ukraine).

Type material: Holotype ♂: Algeria, Oum El Bouaghi forest, 1210m, 35.899, 7.129, pt., iv.2016. Holotype is deposited in collection of Czech University of Life Sciences, Prague, Czech Republic.

Comparison: This species is related to *Sarcophila dayanella* Lehrer, 2003 (Fig. 3) from Syria and *Sarcophila navara* Lehrer, 2003 (Fig. 4) from Israel by a single row of black setae on parafacials, by shortened apical part of cercus and by strongly curved hypophallus, but differs by absence of spines of apical part of cercus, by presence of a vertical row of setae on lower part of surstylus, and pointed aedeagus.

Ecology: Probably, mesophilous forest species.

List of Algerian Sarcophagidae, collected in Oum El Bouaghi forest¹

1. *Metopia* (s.str.) *argyrocephala* (Meigen, 1824)²: 1 ♂.
2. *Paragusia multipunctata* (Rondani, 1859)²: 1 ♂.
3. *Phrosinella* (s. str.) *fedtshenkoi* (Rohdendorf, 1925)²: 1 ♂.
4. *Sarcophila khrokalo* sp. n.²: 1 ♂.
5. *Blaesoxipha rufipes* (Macquart, 1839) [Verves, 1985, 2017]³: 1 ♀.

6. *Helicophagella* (s. str.) *novercoides* Böttcher, 1913²: 3 ♂.
7. *Artamonoviella monspellensia* (Böttcher, 1913)²: 2 ♂.
8. *Heteronychia* (*Ctenodasypygia*) *minima* (Rondani, 1862) [Verves, 2017; Villeneuve, 1911; Whitmore, 2011]: 9 ♂.
9. *H.* (C.) *thirionae* (Lehrer, 1976) [Verves, 2017; Whitmore, 2009]: 2 ♂.
10. *H.* (C.) *uncicurva* Pandellé, 1896²: 1 ♂, 1 ♀.
11. *H.* (C.) *villeneuveana* (Enderlein, 1928) [Enderlein, 1928]: 1 ♂.
12. *H.* (s. str.) *pandellei* (Rohdendorf, 1937) [Rohdendorf, 1937; Verves, 2017]: 3 ♂.
13. *Karovia hirticrus* (Pandellé, 1896) [Böttcher, 1912; Verves, 2017]: 6 ♂.
14. *Myorhina* (s. str.) *nigriventris* (Meigen, 1826) [Séguy, 1941; Verves, 2017]: 7 ♂, 1 ♀.
15. *Thyrsocnema belgiana* Lehrer, 1976²: 1 ♂.
16. *Bercaea africa* (Wiedemann, 1824) [James, 1947; Verves, 2017]: 3 ♂.
17. *Liosarcophaga* (s. str.) *catalunya* Lehrer, 2008²: 1 ♂.
18. *L.* (s. str.) *marshalli* (Parker, 1923) [El-Hawagry & El-Azab, 2019]: 4 ♂.
19. *L.* (s. str.) *portschinskyi* (Rohdendorf, 1937)²: 1 ♂.
20. *L.* (s. str.) *teretirostris* (Pandellé, 1896)²: 8 ♂.

Discussion

A total of 199 sarcophagid species are known from North African region. Regional faunas of North Africa are not studied in detail: their review (including the results of present paper) is given in Table 1. The regional cadastres present not less than 80-90% of full special lists of depleted island ecosystems, such as Azores (17 species), Canary Is. (33), Madeira (7) and Malta (45). Among continental countries, the most of the studies are designated for Egypt (116) and Algeria (84). The faunistic lists at level 20-40% are known for Morocco (49) Tunisia (45) and Libya (24). Only two species are known from the enclave area Ceuta & Melilla.

¹ The sequence of species in the list corresponds to the system of family adopted by Verves (1986).

² * - firstly recorded to Algerian fauna.

³ The references to previous publications about the collection of this species in Algeria are given in square brackets.

Figures 1-4: Male genitalia (lateral view) of *Sarcophila khrokaloae* sp. n. [1. cercus and surstylus; 2. aedeagus and gonites, orig.]; after Lehrer, 2003b: *S. dayaniella* Lehrer, 2003 [3] and *S. navara* Lehrer, 2003 [4]. A. cercus and surstylus; B. aedeagus; C. apical part of hypophallus; D. postgonite; E. pregonite.

Acknowledgements

Author is thankful to Prof., Dr. Sci. Miroslav Barták (Department of Zoology and Fisheries, Faculty of Agrobiolgy, Food and

Natural Resources, Czech University of Life Sciences, Prague, Czech Republic) for sending dry flies.

Table 1

List of species of Sarcophagidae from different North African countries⁴

No.	Species	Countries and islands (in direction from West to East)								
		Azores	Madeira Is.	Canary Is.	Morocco	Spanish Africa (Ceuta & Melilla)	Algeria	Tunisia	Malta	Libya
1	<i>Macronychia</i> (s. str.) <i>lemariei</i> Jacentkovský, 1941	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-
2	<i>M. (Moschusa) polyodon</i> (Meigen, 1824)	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	+	-
(2 sp.) Macronychiinae, sum		-	-	-	1	-	1	-	1	-
3	<i>Senotainia (Arrenopus) albifrons</i> (Rondani, 1859)	-	-	+	-	-	+	+	-	+
4	<i>S. (s. str.) aegyptiaca</i> Rohdendorf, 1935	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+
5	<i>S. (s. str.) caspica</i> Rohdendorf, 1935	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+
6	<i>S. (s. str.) deserta</i> Rohdendorf, 1935	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+
7	<i>S. (s. str.) efflatouni</i> (Rohdendorf, 1935)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+
8	<i>S. (s. str.) tricuspis</i> (Meigen, 1838)	+	-	-	+	-	-	+	+	+
9	<i>Eremasiomya macularis</i> (Wiedemann, 1824)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+
10	<i>E. meridionalis</i> (Rohdendorf, 1927)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+
11	<i>E. nigra</i> Rohdendorf, 1935	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+
12	<i>E. thereomyioides</i> Rohdendorf, 1935	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+
13	<i>Protomiltogramma aegyptiaca</i> (Rohdendorf, 1934)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+
14	<i>P. fasciata</i> (Meigen, 1824)	-	-	+	+	-	+	-	-	+
15	<i>P. immunita</i> (Villeneuve, 1923), comb. n.	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+
16	<i>P. obscurior</i> (Villeneuve, 1916)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+
17	<i>Pterella convergens</i> (Pandellé, 1895)	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-
18	<i>P. grisea</i> (Meigen, 1824)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-
19	<i>P. melanura</i> (Meigen, 1824)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-
20	<i>P. nigrofasciata</i> (Rohdendorf, 1935)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+
21	<i>Achaetocephalon nudum</i> (Rohdendorf, 1934)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+
22	<i>Anacanthothecum testaceifrons</i> (Roser, 1840)	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-
23	<i>Capnopteron africanum</i> (Verves, 1979)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+
24	<i>C. maroccanum</i> (Séguy, 1941)	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	+
25	<i>Cylindrothecum ibericum</i> (Villeneuve, 1912)	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-
26	<i>Efflatounomyia albidopilosa</i> Rohdendorf, 1934	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+
27	<i>E. pardalina</i> Rohdendorf, 1934	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+
28	<i>Miltogramma algira</i> Macquart, 1843	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	+
29	<i>M. aurifrons</i> Dufour, 1850	-	-	+	+	-	+	+	-	+
30	<i>M. brevipila</i> Villeneuve, 1911	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	+
31	<i>M. germari</i> Meigen, 1824	-	-	-	+	-	+	-	-	+
32	<i>M. murina</i> Meigen, 1824	-	-	-	+	-	-	+	+	-

⁴ Legend: “+” – species recorded after previous publications; “*” - species firstly recorded; “-” – species not recorded.

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33	<i>M. oestracea</i> (Fallén, 1820)	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	+	+
34	<i>M. punctata</i> Meigen, 1824	-	-	+	-	-	+	+	-	-	+
35	<i>M. ruficornis</i> Meigen, 1824	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-
36	<i>M. tunesica</i> (Enderlein, 1936)	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-
37	<i>M. villeneuvei</i> Verves, 1982	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+
38	<i>Miltogrammidium albifacies</i> (Villeneuve, 1929)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+
39	<i>M. chivae</i> (Rohdendorf, 1935)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+
40	<i>M. efflatouni</i> (Rohdendorf, 1934)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+
41	<i>M. rutilans</i> (Meigen, 1824)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-
42	<i>Craticulina barbifera</i> (Pandellé, 1895)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+
43	<i>C. bequaerti</i> Venturi, 1958	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	+
44	<i>C. diffusa</i> Villeneuve, 1934	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+
45	<i>C. tabaniformis</i> (Fabricius, 1805)	-	-	-	+	-	+	-	+	+	+
46	<i>Apodacra chrysocephala</i> Rohdendorf, 1925	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+
47	<i>A. seriemaculata</i> Macquart, 1854	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+
48	<i>Xeromyia africana</i> (Rohdendorf, 1930)	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-
49	<i>X. algiralis</i> (Séguy, 1941)	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	+
50	<i>X. dasystigma</i> (Rohdendorf, 1934)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+
51	<i>X. merei</i> (Séguy, 1941)	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-
52	<i>X. orthogona</i> (Rohdendorf, 1925)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+
53	<i>X. stenorhina</i> (Rohdendorf, 1934)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+
54	<i>X. sulcata</i> (Villeneuve, 1933)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+
55	<i>Xerophilomyia cyprica</i> (Rondani, 1859)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+
56	<i>X. nigropicta</i> Rohdendorf, 1934	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+
57	<i>X. plumipes</i> (Villeneuve, 1933)	-	-	-	+	-	-	+	-	-	+
58	<i>Amobia oculata</i> (Zetterstedt, 1844)	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-
59	<i>A. signata</i> (Meigen, 1824)	+	-	+	+	-	+	+	+	+	-
60	<i>Sphecapatodes ornatus</i> Villeneuve, 1912	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	+
61	<i>Dolichotachina marginella</i> (Wiedemann, 1830)	-	-	-	+	-	+	+	-	+	+
62	<i>Hoplcephala hirtifrons</i> (Villeneuve, 1929)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+
63	<i>Prohoplcephala hafezi</i> (Rohdendorf, 1975)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+
64	<i>Metopodia pilicornis</i> (Pandellé, 1895)	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-
65	<i>Alusomyia transfuga</i> Villeneuve, 1933	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+
66	<i>Sphecapatoclea excisa</i> Villeneuve, 1909	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+
67	<i>S. ghoulsensis</i> Rohdendorf, 1975	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+
68	<i>S. minor</i> Villeneuve, 1912	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-
69	<i>Metopia argyrocephala</i> (Meigen, 1824)	-	-	-	-	-	*	-	-	-	-
70	<i>Phrosinella fedtshenkoi</i> Rohdendorf, 1925	-	-	-	-	-	*	-	-	-	-
71	<i>P. nasuta</i> (Meigen, 1824)	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	+	+
72	<i>P. zarudnoji</i> Rohdendorf, 1971	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	*
73	<i>Hilarella hilarella</i> (Zetterstedt, 1844)	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
74	<i>H. stictica</i> (Meigen, 1830)	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-
75	<i>Paragusia albina</i> (Rohdendorf, 1935)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	*
76	<i>P. elegantula</i> (Zetterstedt, 1844)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	*
77	<i>P. multipunctata</i> (Rondani, 1859)	-	-	+	-	-	*	+	+	-	+
78	<i>Taxigramma heteroneura</i> (Meigen, 1830)	-	-	+	+	-	+	-	-	-	+
79	<i>Sphenometopa (Euaraba) claripennis</i> (Villeneuve, 1933)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+
80	<i>S. (E.) efflatouni</i> (Villeneuve, 1933)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+
81	<i>S. (E.) fastuosa</i> (Meigen, 1824)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+
82	<i>S. (Sahararaba) elegans</i> (Rohdendorf, 1971)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+
(80 sp.) Miltogramminae, sum		2	-	8	14	-	23	12	9	7	61

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83	<i>Sarcotachina aegyptiaca</i> Villeneuve, 1910	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	+
84	<i>S. umbrinervis</i> Villeneuve, 1910	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+
(2 sp.) Eumacronychiinae, sum		-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	2
85	<i>Nyctia halterata</i> (Panzer, 1798)	-	-	-	+	-	+	-	+	+	+
86	<i>N. lugubris</i> (Macquart, 1843)	-	-	+	-	-	+	+	+	-	-
87	<i>Agria affinis</i> (Fallén, 1817)	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-
88	<i>Blaesoxiphella brevicornis</i> Villeneuve, 1912	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-
89	<i>Sarcophila khrokaloae</i> sp. n.	-	-	-	-	-	*	-	-	-	-
90	<i>S. latifrons</i> (Fallén, 1817)	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	+	-	-
91	<i>S. meridionalis</i> Rohdendorf et Verves, 1982	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	+	-	+
92	<i>S. navara</i> Lehrer, 2003	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+
93	<i>Wohlfahrtia aschersoni</i> (Enderlein, 1934)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	+
94	<i>W. bella</i> (Macquart, 1839)	-	-	+	+	-	+	+	-	-	+
95	<i>W. brunnipalpis</i> (Macquart, 1851)	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	+
96	<i>W. erythrocerata</i> Villeneuve, 1910	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	+	-
97	<i>W. indigena</i> Villeneuve, 1928	-	-	+	+	-	+	+	-	-	+
98	<i>W. magnifica</i> (Schiner, 1862)	-	-	-	+	-	+	+	-	+	+
99	<i>W. nuba</i> (Wiedemann, 1830)	-	-	-	+	-	-	+	-	-	+
100	<i>W. trina</i> (Wiedemann, 1830)	-	-	+	-	-	+	-	-	+	+
101	<i>W. villeneuvei</i> Salem, 1938	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	+	+
102	<i>Wohlfahrtiodes aemulus</i> Séguy, 1940	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-
103	<i>W. nudus</i> Villeneuve, 1910	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+
(19 sp.) Paramacronychiinae, sum		1	-	5	5	-	13	5	2	7	12
104	<i>Agriella algeriensis</i> (Townsend, 1919)	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	+
105	<i>A. pandellei</i> Villeneuve, 1911	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	-	-	-
106	<i>A. rufescens</i> (Villeneuve, 1928)	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-
107	<i>A. setosa</i> Salem, 1938	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	+	+
108	<i>Agriella tunisia</i> (Pape, 1994)	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-
109	<i>Blaesoxipha cochlearis</i> (Pandellé, 1896)	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-
110	<i>B. colorata</i> Verves, 1985	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-
111	<i>B. dupuisi</i> Léonide et Léonide, 1973	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-
112	<i>B. grylloctona</i> Löw, 1861	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+
113	<i>B. laticornis</i> (Meigen, 1826)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+
114	<i>B. litoralis</i> (Villeneuve, 1911)	-	-	-	+	-	+	-	-	-	-
115	<i>B. misriella</i> Lehrer, 2002	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+
116	<i>B. pygmaea</i> (Zetterstedt, 1844)	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-
117	<i>B. redempta</i> (Pandellé, 1896)	-	-	+	+	-	+	+	+	+	+
118	<i>B. rufipes</i> (Macquart, 1839)	+	-	+	-	-	+	-	-	-	+
119	<i>B. subcochlearis</i> Séguy, 1932	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-
120	<i>B. ungulata</i> (Pandellé, 1896)	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-
121	<i>Servaisia</i> (s. str.) <i>rossica</i> (Villeneuve, 1912)	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-
122	<i>Ravinia pernix</i> (Harris, 1780)	+	-	+	+	-	+	+	+	+	+
123	<i>Helicophagella</i> (s. str.) <i>noverca</i> (Rondani, 1860)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	+
124	<i>H.</i> (s. str.) <i>novercoides</i> (Böttcher, 1913)	-	-	-	-	-	*	-	-	-	+
125	<i>H.</i> (s. str.) <i>rosellei</i> (Böttcher, 1912)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	+
126	<i>H. (Parabellieria) maculata</i> (Meigen, 1835)	+	-	+	+	-	+	+	-	-	+
127	<i>H. (P.) melanura</i> (Meigen, 1826)	-	-	+	+	-	+	+	+	+	+
128	<i>Beziella (Brasia) kadeisi</i> (Salem, 1938)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+
129	<i>Artamonoviella monspellensia</i> (Böttcher, 1913)	-	-	-	-	-	*	+	+	-	-
130	<i>Discachaeta kunonis</i> Pape, 1986	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
131	<i>Heteronychia (Asceloctis) amputata</i> (Pape, 1990)	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

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132	<i>H. (A.) balanina</i> (Pandellé, 1896)	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-
133	<i>H. (A.) desertorum</i> (Salem, 1935)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+
134	<i>H. (A.) ferox</i> (Villeneuve, 1908)	-	-	+	+	-	+	+	+	-	-
135	<i>H. (A.) mariutana</i> (Salem, 1935)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+
136	<i>H. (Boettcherella) setinervis</i> (Rondani, 1860)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+
137	<i>H. (Ctenodasyphygia) graeca</i> (Rohdendorf, 1937)	-	-	-	-	-	*	-	-	-	-
138	<i>H. (C.) minima</i> (Rondani, 1862)	-	-	-	+	-	+	+	+	-	+
139	<i>H. (C.) penicillata</i> (Villeneuve, 1907)	-	-	-	+	-	+	+	+	-	-
140	<i>H. (C.) santospintosi</i> (Lehrer & Báez, 1986)	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
141	<i>H. (C.) siciliensis</i> (Böttcher, 1913)	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	+
142	<i>H. (C.) thirionae</i> (Lehrer, 1976)	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-
143	<i>H. (C.) tricolor</i> (Villeneuve, 1908)	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
144	<i>H. (C.) uncicurva</i> (Pandellé, 1896)	+	-	+	-	+	*	+	+	-	-
145	<i>H. (C.) villeneuveana</i> (Enderlein, 1928)	-	-	-	+	-	+	+	+	-	-
146	<i>H. (s. str.) amica</i> Peris, González-Mora et Mingo, 1998	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-
147	<i>H. (s. str.) benaci</i> (Böttcher, 1913)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-
148	<i>H. (s. str.) bulgarica</i> (Enderlein, 1936)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-
149	<i>H. (s. str.) consanguinea</i> (Rondani, 1860)	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-
150	<i>H. (s. str.) depressifrons</i> (Zetterstedt, 1845)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-
151	<i>H. (s. str.) haemorrhoides</i> (Böttcher, 1913)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-
152	<i>H. (s. str.) metopina</i> (Villeneuve, 1908)	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
153	<i>H. (s. str.) pandellei</i> (Rohdendorf, 1937)	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	-	-	-
154	<i>H. (s. str.) proxima</i> (Rondani, 1860)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-
155	<i>H. (s. str.) tunisiae</i> (Whitmore, 2011)	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-
156	<i>H. (Pandelleola) filia</i> (Rondani, 1860)	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	+	-	-
157	<i>H. (P.) sicilia</i> (Pape, 1996)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-
158	<i>Karovia hirticrus</i> (Pandellé, 1896)	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	+	-	-
159	<i>Notoecus longestylatus</i> (Strobl, 1906)	-	-	-	+	-	+	+	-	-	-
160	<i>Krameromyia anaces</i> (Walker, 1849)	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-
161	<i>Myorhina (s. str.) nigriventris</i> (Meigen, 1826)	-	-	-	+	-	+	+	+	+	-
162	<i>M. (s. str.) soror</i> (Rondani, 1860)	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
163	<i>Pandelleana berberina</i> Lehrer, 2003	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-
164	<i>Pseudothyrsocnema spinosa</i> (Villeneuve, 1912)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+
165	<i>Sarina sexpunctata</i> (Fabricius, 1805)	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
166	<i>Thyrsocnema belgiana</i> Lehrer, 1976	-	-	-	-	-	*	-	-	-	-
167	<i>T. incisilobata</i> (Pandellé, 1896)	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-
168	<i>Transvaalomomyia rohdendorfi</i> (Salem, 1936)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+
169	<i>Phytosarcophaga (s. str.) destructor</i> (Malloch, 1929)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	+
170	<i>Bercaea africa</i> (Wiedemann, 1824)	+	+	+	+	-	+	+	+	+	+
171	<i>Liopygia (Engelisca) surcoufi</i> (Villeneuve, 1913)	+	-	-	-	-	+	+	-	-	+
172	<i>L. (Jantia) crassipalpis</i> (Macquart, 1839)	+	+	+	+	-	+	+	+	+	+
173	<i>L. (Thomsonia) argyrostoma</i> (Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830)	+	+	+	-	-	+	+	+	-	+
174	<i>Liosarcophaga (Curranea) tibialis</i> (Macquart, 1851)	+	+	+	-	-	+	+	+	+	+
175	<i>L. (s. str.) aegyptica</i> (Salem, 1935)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+
176	<i>L. (s. str.) catalunya</i> Lehrer, 2008	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-
177	<i>L. (s. str.) deviedmai</i> (Lehrer & Baez, 1986)	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
178	<i>L. (s. str.) dux</i> (Thomson, 1869)	+	-	+	+	-	-	+	+	+	+

179	<i>L.</i> (s. str.) <i>ismailiana</i> Lehrer, 1998	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+
180	<i>L.</i> (s. str.) <i>jacobsoni</i> (Rohdendorf, 1937)	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	+
181	<i>L.</i> (s. str.) <i>madeirensis</i> (Schiner, 1869)	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
182	<i>L.</i> (s. str.) <i>marshalli</i> (Parker, 1923)	-	-	-	+	-	+	+	+	-	+
183	<i>L.</i> (s. str.) <i>mennae</i> (El-Ahmady, Taha, Soliman & El-Hawagry, 2018)	-	-	-	-	-	*	-	-	-	-
184	<i>L.</i> (s. str.) <i>parkeri</i> (Rohdendorf, 1937)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+
185	<i>L.</i> (s. str.) <i>pharaonis</i> (Rohdendorf, 1934)	-	-	-	+	-	-	+	-	-	+
186	<i>L.</i> (s. str.) <i>portschinskyi</i> (Rohdendorf, 1937)	-	-	-	+	-	*	-	-	-	-
187	<i>L.</i> (s. str.) <i>redux</i> (Walker, 1849)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+
188	<i>L.</i> (s. str.) <i>teretirostris</i> (Pandellé, 1896)	-	-	-	+	-	*	-	+	-	-
189	<i>L.</i> (s. str.) <i>tuberosa</i> (Pandellé, 1896)	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
190	<i>L.</i> (<i>Pandelleisca</i>) <i>similis</i> (Meade, 1876)	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
191	<i>L.</i> (<i>Pharaonops</i>) <i>tewfiki</i> (Salem, 1940)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+
192	<i>Parasarcophaga</i> (s. str.) <i>albiceps</i> (Meigen, 1826)	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	+
193	<i>P.</i> (s. str.) <i>hirtipes</i> (Wiedemann, 1830)	-	-	-	+	-	+	-	-	-	+
194	<i>Stackelbergeola</i> <i>grueti</i> Lehrer, 2000	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+
195	<i>Sarcophaga</i> <i>carnaria</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-
196	<i>S.</i> <i>lehmanni</i> Müller, 1922	-	-	-	+	-	+	+	+	-	+
197	<i>S.</i> <i>marcelleclercqi</i> Lehrer, 1975	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-
198	<i>S.</i> <i>subvicina</i> Rohdendorf, 1937	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-
199	<i>S.</i> <i>variegata</i> (Scopoli, 1763)	-	-	-	+	-	+	-	+	-	+
(96 sp.) Sarcophaginae sum		14	7	20	29	2	46	28	31	10	41
Sarcophagidae total		17	7	33	49	2	84	45	43	24	116

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